
105. Wolf–Rayet stars

WOLF–RAYET STARS represents the final He-burning phase in the evolution of massive O stars of initial mass $\geq 25M_{\odot}$ (Maeder, 1996). In addition to the Doppler-broadened He lines in the stellar winds, the ejection process uncovers first the nitrogen-rich products of the CNO fusion cycle (WN stars), and later the carbon-rich layer due to He burning (WC and WO-type stars). The class is named after their discovery by two members of the Paris Observatory in 1867.

At the end of the core-He burning, the star explodes as a supernova. The outer shell of reaction products is expelled into the interstellar medium, and the accompanying core collapse results in either a neutron star or a black hole. The Wolf–Rayet phase is therefore likely to be the last observable stage before collapse.

Beneath the dense winds that often hide the stellar surface, Wolf–Rayet stars have $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 30\,000 - 150\,000$ K, $R \sim 1 - 15R_{\odot}$, and $L \sim 10^5 - 10^6 L_{\odot}$. They have high mass-loss rates of $1 - 10 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with terminal outflow velocities of $1000 - 3000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (e.g. Crowther 2006).

Many Wolf–Rayet (and indeed other O-type) stars lie well outside their birth places in open clusters and OB associations, signalled by their rapid space motions of 100 km s^{-1} or more, and by their large distances from the Galactic plane. The two most plausible theories for the origin of such ‘runaway stars’ are through binary-supernova events, or via cluster ejection (essay #81).

DESPITE THE FACT that their characteristic spectra are easily recognisable to large distances, Wolf–Rayet stars are rare, with only around 1200 estimated to exist in our Galaxy. Van der Hucht (2006) listed just 298 (designated WR n, with suffices), of which 24 were in the open cluster Westerlund 1, and around 60 were in open clusters near the Galactic centre.

Today more than 800 are known, with some 150 in the LMC (designated BAT-99 n, and sometimes by the Radcliffe R number, e.g. R136a1), and just 12 in the LMC (designated AB n). The majority are of sub-type WN.

Studies of Wolf–Rayet stars are mainly aimed at clarifying the still-uncertain late stages of stellar evolution.

OF THE 200 or so Galactic Wolf–Rayet stars known around 1990, Hipparcos observed 67, including almost all those brighter than $V = 12$. Amongst the applications of the Hipparcos results was a study of the runaway stars by Moffat et al. (1998), who concluded that the observations were in reasonable agreement with the cluster-ejection scenario.

JUST ONE Wolf–Rayet star, γ^2 Vel (WR 11, one of the components of the quadruple system γ Vel), by far the brightest and nearest known, had a significant Hipparcos parallax, $\pi_{\text{Hip}} = 3.88 \pm 0.53$ mas. At just 7σ , it yielded a distance of $d = 258^{+41}_{-31}$ pc, compared with the previous ground-based estimate of 450–460 pc, which had been considered as rather secure.

In subsequent discussions (e.g. van der Hucht et al. 1997; Schaerer et al. 1997), it was argued that adoption of the Hipparcos distance would assist in solving the problem of the mass-loss rate derived from the radio data, but also implying that it could no longer be associated with the Vela OB2 association.

Unfortunately, the apparent magnitude of γ^2 Vel, $V = 1.8$ mag, places it amongst the small number of the very brightest stars for which a Gaia parallax is not yet available (e.g. Sahlmann et al., 2016).

DESPITE THEIR rarity, Wolf–Rayet stars have an enormous influence on their environment. Due to their high temperatures, they produce large numbers of ionising photons, and their huge mass-loss deeply enriches the surrounding interstellar medium with metals.

However, these final stages of massive-star evolution remain poorly understood. Major gaps in understanding arise from uncertainties in the stellar mass loss in the Wolf–Rayet phase, angular momentum loss, internal mixing processes, the binary fraction, close-binary evolution with mass exchange, common-envelope evolution, and stellar mergers (e.g. Hamann et al., 2019).

All these factors also depend on metallicity. Thus, quantifying their impact is of particular importance for a variety of astrophysical applications.

TO OBTAIN their luminosities, of course, their distances need to be known. And most of the distances to the Wolf–Rayet stars in our Galaxy were only very poorly constrained before Gaia.

Today, a number of papers are addressing updates in the physical properties, cluster membership, or run-away status of individual Wolf–Rayet stars using the Gaia data, e.g. WR 6 (Gvaramadze, 2020); WR 16 (Cichowski et al., 2020); and WR 36 (Rocha et al., 2020).

TWO PAPERS have used the Gaia DR2 distances to revisit the physical properties, notably luminosities and mass-loss rates, for the two main classes: the WC/WO population, and the WN population.

Both populations are, I should first note, subdivided into spectral subtypes (WC4...WN11; WN2...WN11) depending on temperature (and the associated emission lines), with the hotter spectral sub-classes often described as ‘early’ (WNE, WCE) and the cooler ones as ‘late’ (WNL, WCL), consistent with the convention for other spectral types. To complicate matters further, there is a strong tendency for WNE stars to be hydrogen-poor, while the spectra of WNL stars frequently show hydrogen lines; and their properties differ significantly.

Sander et al. (2019) used Gaia DR2 distances to re-examine the properties of the 56 stars from the Galactic WC population previously defined by Sander et al. (2012), according to subtype (WC4, WC5, etc.). Their resulting location in the Galactic plane is shown below.

A significant finding, and one contrasting with previous assumptions, is that WC stars of the same subtype can vary significantly in absolute magnitude. The Gaia-based luminosities, $\log(L/L_{\odot}) = 4.9 - 6.0$, indicates that WC stars likely form from a broader initial mass range than previously assumed. Similar results were found for their three Galactic WO stars, implying that ‘...only a complete revision of the spectral analysis with new atmosphere models... can help to resolve the discrepancies.’

And as a consequence of the new luminosities, their mass-loss rates also have to be revised. Sander et al. (2019) concluded that, while the evolutionary status of Galactic WC and WO stars as evolved, core-helium burning objects is not under question, many details of the evolutionary path toward this status remain uncertain.

A SIMILAR APPROACH, also using distances from Gaia DR2, was applied to the Galactic WN population by Hamann et al. (2019). This has allowed a comparison for their 55 single stars in common with the earlier study by Hamann et al. (2006), for which the distances to the individual objects were again only poorly known. Their revised location in the Galactic plane is shown below.

While the DR2 distances are typically some 10% smaller than the earlier study, differences reach -2.6 mag in distance modulus in the most extreme cases. The correlations between mass-loss rate and luminosity show a large scatter, while the slopes of the $\log L - \log \dot{M}$ correlations are shallower than found previously.

The empirical Hertzsprung–Russell diagram confirms a previously established dichotomy between the hydrogen-free early WN subtypes, which are located on the hot side of the Zero Age Main Sequence (ZAMS), and the late WN subtypes, which show hydrogen and reside mostly at cooler temperatures than the ZAMS.

With the new Gaia distances, the distribution of stellar luminosities is more continuous than previously suspected. The WNL stars with hydrogen are still found to be typically more luminous than the hydrogen-free WNEs, but there is a range of luminosities ($\log L/L_{\odot} \approx 5.5 \dots 6.1$) where both subclasses overlap.

And neither state-of-the-art single-star evolutionary models (Ekström et al., 2012), nor binary scenarios, could provide a fully satisfactory explanation for the parameters of these objects and their location in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram.

DISTANCES of 383 Galactic Wolf–Rayet stars from Gaia DR2, combined with H II region scale heights, were used by Rate & Crowther (2020) to identify 31 at large distances from the mid-plane ($z > \pm 156$ pc) as potential runaways. Only four are WN8–9, in contrast to the findings of Rosslowe & Crowther (2015).

Rate et al. (2020) used the Gaia DR2 parallaxes and proper motions to revisit their membership of Galactic clusters and associations. They found that only 18–36% of 553 Wolf–Rayet stars away from the Galactic centre are located in clusters or OB associations, implying that at least 64% of the known disk population are isolated.

THE GAIA DATA will clearly continue to have a significant impact on future modelling of many aspects of this important late stage of stellar evolution.